

Codex Saqqara

FRANCESCO ARDAN DAL RÌ, Conservatory of Music F. A. Bonporti, Italy

FRANCESCA ZANGHELLINI, Conservatory of Music C. Monteverdi, Italy

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1 PROGRAM NOTES

Codex Saqqara is a cycle of five semi-improvised musical pieces for live coding and electric violin. Here, for duration reasons, we present a short excerpt. The interaction between the two performers takes place through a system that allows the violinist to record and overdub up to five samples in real-time, which are then processed and organized into structures by the live coder. In this way, the two musicians interact with each other's musical space, taking on different musical roles during the performance, such as soloists, orchestrators or accompanists. Given its extemporaneous nature, the piece is composed from-scratch, following a series of macro-structures determined beforehand. This submission accompanies a paper regarding the system used, along with some reflections that emerged during the rehearsals for this performance.

Fig. 1. A snippet of the performance.

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2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

This project is formed by Francesco Ardan Dal Ri - Return_Nihil (live coding) and Francesca Zanghellini (electric violin). Both musicians have a strong background in contemporary music and they are used to performing together in live electronics and improvisational contexts. With this project, they would like to further explore both the possibilities of co-creation and shared agency offered by novel technological means, both the possible interactions between two different musical practices. As such, the interactive ecosystem used in this performance has been developed through various rehearsals, exploring different musical situations, at the end of which they discussed their perspective, their performative strategies, and the affordances/constraints of the ecosystem.

3 PERFORMANCE NOTES

Unfortunately, we will not be able to attend the in-presence conference due to geographical distance and lack of funding. As such, in the next section, we provide a video of our performance.

4 MEDIA LINKS

- Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DeXHBE2wFgg&feature=youtu.be>

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

The systems used in this submission have been developed using FLOSS. The code is open-source and freely available at https://github.com/return-nihil/Live_Coding/tree/main/Duo and can be easily adapted for anyone to use it, without the explicit need of buying specific hardware or operating complex mods on traditional musical instruments. Furthermore, we declare no conflict of interest.